

SATISFACTION OF WOMEN SELF HELP GROUPS ON MICRO CREDIT - AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Dr. S. Shanmugapriya

Assistant Professor in Commerce (Aided), NGM College
(Autonomous), Pollachi, Tamilnadu

Introduction:

Micro credit is a financial innovation with origination in developing countries to enable the impoverished people engaged in self employment projects to generate an income, to build wealth and reduce poverty. Micro credit has its origins in the early eras of civilization. It was out of necessity that man became aware of the benefits of lending and borrowing. Much before the advent of money and banking, the practice of lending was prevalent in kind. For example, a farmer gave some seeds to another on the condition that the recipient would return the seeds with some extra quantity. This little extra, today known as interest was the cost of micro borrowing. The micro credit programme was introduced in India in the year 1992. Over years, since inception, there has been a tremendous growth in respect of formation of SHGs, granting of bank loans and refinance through NABARD.

Review of Literature:

Dr. K. Sudha Rani, et.al. (2002) in their study identified five aspects among women namely solidarity, strength, mobilization, collective action and self confidence are the major factors positively contributing in increasing their decision making power.

C. K. Gariyali and S. K. Vettivel (2004) in their study, found that the SHGs are not just a conduit for the loans, although loans are a critical milestone on the road map of the SHG's healthy growth and empowerment. The women often complain that they are very active initially but due to delays in obtaining credit they become lazy. Though, an alternative way of enhancing the lending channels need to be explored, the rural cooperative banking network needs to be encouraged to lend to the SHGs, which can make credit available to them at their doorsteps.

Dr. Ranjan Chaudhuri et.al, (2014) in their study identified the MFI is an organization that provides financial services to the poor. Provision of thrift, credit and other financial services and products of very small amounts to the poor in rural, semi-urban or urban areas for enabling them to raise their income level and improving living standards are the major factors influencing its successiveness.

Objectives of the Study:

- The study has been carried on with the following objectives.
- ✓ To study the socio economic profiles of self help group members.
 - ✓ To examine the influence of socio economic factors with the level of satisfaction among self help group members.
 - ✓ To make suitable suggestions for the development of SHG based on the findings of the study.

Methodology:

This study is related to SHG which are functioning in Pollachi Taluk of Coimbatore District popularly known as "Switzerland of Coimbatore". Total area of Pollachi is divided into 3 major blocks namely Pollachi north block, Pollachi south block, and municipality block only. It is surrounded by 137 major villages where north block covers 129 villages and south block contains 142 villages in the south. The municipality is to be constituted with 36 wards. Cultivation of coconut tree and coir industries plays

as the key occupation in Pollachi Taluk. In Pollachi, nearly 2000 Self Help Groups are under the control being organized by HIGH CLASS NGOs.

Sampling:

Primary Data have been collected from 150 self help group members and since, most of the members are illiterate interviews schedule was conducted during the period from April 2014 to September 2015. One hundred fifty members residing in and around Pollachi have been selected through simple random sampling method from the HIGH CLASS NGO through interview schedule in Pollachi. The field study was conducted with members of NGO, through interviews to obtain information.

Frame Work of Analysis:

To identify the socio – economic profile of the members the variable such as place, age, marital status, educational qualification, community, type of family, earning members were taken for the analysis

Analysis	Variables	No. of Sample Respondents	Percentage
Place	Rural	80	53.33
	Urban	70	46.67
Age	20-30 yrs	25	16.66
	31-40 yrs	55	36.67
	Above 40 yrs	70	46.67
Marital Status	Unmarried	15	10
	Married	121	80.67
	Widow	14	9.3
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	68	45.33
	Up to HSC	70	46.67
	Degree / Diploma	10	6.67
	Post Graduate	2	1.3
	Others	0	0
Community	OC	5	3.33
	BC	70	46.67
	MBC	19	12.67
	SC	56	37.33
Type of Family	Joint Family	33	22
	Nuclear Family	117	78
Earning Members	One	12	8
	Two	71	47.33
	Above Two	67	44.67
Annual Income	Up to Rs.15000	33	22
	Rs.15001-Rs.30,000	27	18
	Rs.30,001-Rs.50,000	18	12
	Above Rs.50,000	22	14.66

The personal profile of Self Help Groups indicates that out of total sample respondents taken for the study, majority (53.33%) of the sample respondents belong to rural area and about (46.66) percent belong to the age group of above 40 years and above. Majority of the sample respondents (80.67%) are married women. Majorities (46.67%) of women in SHG are educated and they are upto higher secondary level only. Most of the sample respondents (40%) are engaged in business. Majority of the sample respondents (46.67) percent comes under BC category. About a high percentage (78%)

of members belong to the nuclear family. About (47.33) percent of women SHG have revealed that there are only two earning members in a family. The majority of (33%) of respondents are found to have an annual income up to Rs.15000.

Factors Influencing Level of Satisfaction of WSHGs - Chi Square Analysis:

Chi- square test is applied to find out if there is any significant relationship between various personal factors and the factors influencing level of satisfaction of wshgs.

Area	Variables	Level of Satisfaction			Total	d.f: 2 Calculated χ^2 Value: 15.472 **
		Low	Medium	High		
Area	Rural	0(00.00)	46(61.33)	29(38.67)	75(100.00)	
	Urban	2(02.67)	64(85.33)	9(12.00)	75 (100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Age	Up to 30 Years	0(00.00)	20(80.00)	5(20.00)	25(100.00)	d.f: 4 Calculated χ^2 Value: 10.677 *
	31 – 40 Years	0(00.00)	47 (85.45)	8(14.55)	55 (100.00)	
	Above 40 Years	2(02.86)	43(61.43)	25(35.71)	70(100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Marital Status	Unmarried	0(00.00)	12(80.00)	3(20.00)	15(100.00)	d.f:4 Calculated χ^2 Value: 6.512 **
	Married	2(01.65)	84(69.42)	35(28.93)	121(100.00)	
	Widow	0(00.00)	14(100.00)	0(00.00)	14(100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	0(00.00)	50(74.63)	17(25.37)	67 (100.00)	d.f:6 Calculated χ^2 Value:6.779 **
	Up to H.Sc.,	2(02.82)	49(69.01)	20(28.17)	71(100.00)	
	Degree / Diploma	0(00.00)	10(100.00)	0(00.00)	10 (100.00)	
	Post Graduate	0(00.00)	1(50.00)	1(50.00)	2(100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Occupation	Agriculture	1(02.94)	16(47.06)	17 (50.00)	34(100.00)	d.f:8 Calculated χ^2 Value:33.389 *
	Business	1(01.67)	55(91.67)	4(6.67)	60(100.00)	
	Profession	0(00.00)	9(90.00)	1(10.00)	10(100.00)	
	Coolie	0(00.00)	22(57.89)	16(42.11)	38(100.00)	
	Housewife	0(00.00)	8(100.00)	0(00.00)	8(100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Type of Family	Joint	0(00.00)	31(73.81)	11(26.19)	42(100.00)	d.f:2 Calculated χ^2 Value:0.796 ** d.f:4 Calculated χ^2 Value:2.262 **
	Nuclear	2(01.85)	79(73.15)	27 (25.00)	108(100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Earning Member	One	0(00.00)	11(91.67)	1(08.33)	12(100.00)	
	Two	1(01.41)	51(71.83)	19(26.76)	71(100.00)	
	Three	1(01.49)	48 (71.64)	18 (26.87)	67 (100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	
Annual Income	Up to 15000	0(00.00)	9(75.00)	3(25.00)	12 (100.00)	d.f:6 Calculated χ^2 Value:4.282 **
	15001- 30000	1(02.38)	33(78.57)	8(19.05)	42(100.00)	
	30001-50000	0(00.00)	49 (74.24)	17(25.76)	66(100.00)	
	Above 50000	1(03.33)	19(63.33)	10(33.33)	(100.00)	
	Total	2	110	38	150	

Of eight variables applied for identifying the major factors influencing the level of satisfaction of Women Self Help Groups, two variables namely area of residence, occupation are found to be highly significant at one per cent level whereas five variables namely age, marital status, educational qualification, type of family, annual income are found to be highly significant at five per cent level. The calculated chi-square value is greater than the table value at one per cent level; where there exist a highly significant association between area of residence, occupation and level of satisfaction. The calculated chi-square value is greater than the table value at five per cent level; there

exist a highly significant association between age, marital status, educational qualification, type of family, annual income and level of satisfaction.

To measure the level of satisfaction of Self Help Group members various factors like place of residence, age, marital status, type of family, annual income etc., are analyzed. Scaling technique was used to find out the level of satisfaction of the sample respondents.

Level of Satisfaction	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Low	2	1.34
Medium	110	73.43
High	38	25.33
Total	150	100

It is revealed from the table that the level of satisfaction was found to be low with reference to 2(1.34%) of sample respondents; wherein about 110 (73.43%) of respondents, possess medium level of satisfaction; and only 38(25.33%) of sample respondents are highly satisfied. It is clear from the above table that the majority of sample respondents have medium level of satisfaction.

Suggestions:

Government should take necessary steps to bring more numbers of educated persons in self help group and also the NGOs and government should develop saving habits among self help group members. NGOs should take more steps to motivate members to join in SHGs. Most of the members are not willing to participate in social work. So NGOs and government should educate about awareness of the social responsibilities. Most talented SHG members should come forward to start NGOs. In order to start a new business loans are not sanctioned at proper time and more loans should be given to start new business. It is widely spoken that self help members fail in many areas they must be concentrated and proper guidance and counseling programmers to be arranged. Mostly uneducated people joint in self help group to avail loan from the bank to utilize mere subsidy granted by government. But There is no cooperation between members in the groups this habit must be avoided. Few educated person cheat the illiterate member so there must be a proper review meeting to avoid the frauds. Most of the members are married in SHG so more chances should be given to unmarried ladies (i.e. youngsters) for the development of economic status of women.

Conclusion:

It is no wonder, self help group shows the right path to lakhs of young educated and uneducated both rural and urban women to lead a better life. Now idle women from rural areas are earning money for their better being, self help group has opened the eyes of the young rural women entrepreneur to start their business in almost each and every used field which they previously worried to undertake. Self help group has registered a good record in improving the saving habits, income generation, social status and standard of living. The problem related to women can be effectively tackled only by bringing about a social awakening.

References:

1. C. K. Gariyali and S. K. Vettivel, (2004), "Women's Own the Self-Help", pp97-112
2. A. Venkatachalam and A. Jeyaprakash, (October 2004), Self-Help Group in Dindigul District, Kisan World, pp.29-30
3. J. M. Arul Kamaraj, (November 2005), "Self-Help Groups New Mantra for Empowerment", Readers Shelf, Vol.2, issue No.2, pp. 13-16. 109.

4. Smita G. Sabhlok, (June 2006), "Self-Help as a Strategy for Women's Development in India", the University of Melbourne, Australia, pp. 1-26.
5. Subah Singh Yadav, (September 2006), "Self-Help Group Movement in Rajasthan Bright Prospects", Kurukshetra, pp.26-28.
6. Dr. P. Sreelaksmhi, et.al. (2013) "Empowerment through Microfinance" Professional Banker, Vol.No.VIII, pp.51-53.
7. Dr. S. Banumathy (2005), "Self Help Groups and Banks Linkage", www.yahoo.com
8. Dr. K. Sudha Rani, et.al. (2002),"SHGs micro Credit and Empowerment", www.google.com
9. Dr. B. K. Swain (2010) "Social Empowerment of Rural Mass through Self-Help Groups" Professional Banker, Vol.No.VIII, pp.49-52.
10. Sreyashi Sen (2012), "Micro credit: A Reality Check". www.google.com
11. A. Saraswathy et.al, (2009),"Micro-Finance in Krishnagiri District: A tool For Poverty Alleviation", Indian Journal of Marketing, pp.47-57.
12. Dr. Ranjan Chaudhuri et.al, (2014), "Conceptualizing micro Finance Initiatives in India Using SAP- LAP Model: A New Paradigm in Marketing Engineering", Indian Journal of Marketing, pp.23- 29.